

ISic3263

Fragmentary funerary inscription of Marcus Vipsanius Phoebus

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Serena Agodi,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 232

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 30.5 cm

Width 40 cm

Depth 4 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 25-40 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (αταχθονίοις)
2. Μ (ἄρκος) Βειψάνιος
3. Φοῖβος ἔζησ (εν) ἔτη
4. κς πατήρ καὶ μή
5. τηρ υἱῷ εὐσεβεῖ

Apparatus

Translation (en)

To the gods of the underworld. Markos Beipsanios Phoibos (= Marcus Vipsanios Phoebus) lived for 26 years. His father and mother (set this up) for their devoted son.

Translation (it)

Agli dei sotterranei. Marco Vipsanio Febo visse 26 anni. Il padre e la madre (lo costruirono) per il

loro figlio devoto.

Commentary

The style of the inscription is quite particular, with variety in letter forms (e.g. the change in the letter E), the frequent use of ligatures (letters joined together), and hederæ (ivy leaves) to separate words. Although written in Greek, the text echoes Latin practices, such as the abbreviation Θ K (= D M) and also the abbreviation of the Latin praenomen. The spelling of Vipsanius as Beipsanios reflects the common practice from at least the first century AD of transcribing the Latin v as Greek β (although the precise phonetic sound of both letters at this date remains uncertain). On the name Vipsanius, see ISic0383 (inv. no.350).

Digital identifiers:

TM 645544

PHI 316242

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3263. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357967>